

Project Deliverable

Project Number: 325275	Project Acronym: SAPPHIRE	Project Title: System Automation of PEMFCs with Prognostics and Health management for Improved Reliability and Economy
Instrument: Collaborative Project (CP)		Thematic Priority FUEL CELL AND HYDROGEN JOINT UNDERTAKING
Title: First Year Workshop		
Contractual Delivery Date: April 30, 2014		Actual Delivery Date: December 10, 2014
Start date of project: May 1, 2013		Duration: 36 months
Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable: ENSMM		Document version: Version 1.1
Organisation notes:		

Dissemination level (Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Seventh Framework Programme)		
PU	Public	PU Public
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)	
RE	Restricted to a group defined by the consortium (including the Commission)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	

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Abstract :

The first workshop of the SAPPHIRE Project was held in Coimbra, Portugal, the 26th of October, as an invited session of the international IEEE VPPC (350 attendees). It gathered 30 attendees to listen to 6 presentations and was chaired by two SAPPHIRE partners. The workshop was advertised on the conference website, the booklet and the proceedings USB keys. The full articles related to the 5 scientific presentations will be available on-line on the IEEE-Xplore website.

Keywords :

Workshop, Invited Session, International IEEE conference, visibility

Revision History

Rev.	Date	Description	Author (Organisation)
1.0	2014-12-10	Complete draft	Marie-Cécile Péra (UFC)
1.1	2014-12-10	Minor adjustments	Federico Zenith (SINTEF)

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1 Introduction

Work package 8 of the SAPPHIRE project deals with dissemination and exploitation. Task 8.3 consists in the organization of workshops. Two workshops are scheduled at Month 12 and Month 36. The first one was postponed to take place in link with an IEEE international conference and was held the 26th of October 2014, in Coimbra, Portugal.

2 Organization of the first SAPPHIRE workshop

The workshop was postponed from Month 12 to Month 18 in order to be linked to an international conference and to increase its visibility, at the first semestrial meeting. The choice of the Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference (VPPC), in Coimbra, Portugal was confirmed at the second semestrial meeting.

The workshop was organised as an invited session of the IEEE VPPC. It was entitled “Invited Session European Project SAPPHIRE: Prognostics and Health Management of fuel cells”. It took place the 26th of October 2014, the first day of the conference from 15:00 pm to 19:00 pm. (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Screen print of the IEEE VPPC program from the IEEE VPPC 2014 website (www.vppc2014.org)

The workshop was announced in the detailed program of the special sessions on the website and the booklet of the conference (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Screen print of the IEEE VPPC special sessions program from the IEEE VPPC 2014 website (www.vppc2014.org)

Six presentations were given. The first one was the general presentation of the SAPPHIRE project being given by the coordinator. The 5 following ones were scientific presentations on the results already obtained within the SAPPHIRE Project, as well as on prognostic results (Figure 3). The session was chaired by two partners of the SAPPHIRE project. About 30 persons attended the session.

As an invited session, the speakers were individually asked to present by the organization of the workshop. Furthermore, full articles were written except for the general presentation of the SAPPHIRE project and followed the regular reviewing process of the conference.

In order to increase the visibility of the SAPPHIRE Project, a modified draft of the slides was proposed to the speakers, mixing the format of the conference and the logos of the project and the EU (Figure 4).

Time	Invited Session	Amphitheater
15:00-19:00	chairs <i>Prof. Marie-Cécile Pera, University of Franche Comté, France</i> <i>Prof. Frano Barbir, University of Split, Croatia</i>	
IS1-1	Presentation of the SAPPHIRE project Federico Zenith	
IS1-2	Analysis of Fuel Cell Stacks Degradation by Polarization Change Curves D. Bezmalinovic, G. Magazinovic, B. Simic, V. Mitrovic and F. Barbir	
IS1-3	Controllability of a micro combined heat and power fuel-cell system for lifetime maximisation Federico Zenith, Johannes Tjønnås, Ivar J. Halvorsen	
<i>Coffee Break</i>		
IS1-4	Static and dynamic modeling of a PEMFC for prognostics purpose Elodie Lechartier, Rafael Gouriveau, Marie-Cécile Péra, Daniel Hissel, Noureddine Zerhouni	
IS1-5	Performing accelerated stress tests resulting in electrocatalyst degradation in fuel cell stacks Merle Klages, Joachim Scholta	
IS1-6	Fuel Cells Remaining Useful Lifetime forecasting using Echo State Network S. Morando, S. Jemei, R. Gouriveau, N. Zerhouni, D. Hissel	

Figure 3: Screen print of the IEEE VPPC special sessions program from the IEEE VPPC 2014 booklet (www.vppc2014.org)

IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference
"Spreading E-Mobility Everywhere"
October 27-30, 2014 – Coimbra, Portugal <http://www.vppc2014.org>

Lecture Layout
(Title of the presentation)

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SAPPHIRE

Figure 4: Model of the slides for the SAPPHIRE invited session at the VPPC 2014 Conference

The full articles sent on time to the organization of the conference (3/5) were provided to all the participants (about 350 persons) of the conference on the USB key proceedings. All the articles will be available on-line on the IEEE-Xplore website, providing a high visibility to the presented results beyond the workshop itself.

3 Conclusion

The first workshop of the SAPPHIRE Project was held in Coimbra, Portugal, the 26th of October, as an invited session of the international IEEE VPPC (350 attendees). It gathered 30 attendees to listen to 6 presentations and was chaired by two SAPPHIRE partners. The workshop was advertised on the conference website, the booklet and the proceeding USB keys. The full articles related to the 5 scientific presentations will be available on-line on the IEEE-Xplore website.